

1 Title: **Litter-inhabiting fungi show high level of specialization towards biopolymers composing plant**
2 **and fungal biomass**

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26 **Abstract**

27

28 Fungi are recognized as efficient decomposers of biopolymers contained in soil or litter, but not all
29 saprotrophic taxa are equally efficient in accessing various C sources. While many fungi may be considered
30 generalists that are able to utilize complex biomass of plant, bacterial and fungal origin, it is less clear
31 which of the individual biopolymers that compose these substrates they utilize. Here we analysed fungal
32 communities in forest topsoil enriched in bags with polymers composing plant (cellulose, xylan,
33 glucomannan, pectin, lignin) and fungal (chitin, β -1,3-glucan, and β -1,3-1,6-glucan) biomass along with
34 fungal abundance and the activity of enzymes. There was a high degree of specialization among
35 saprotrophs, each biopolymer being preferred by distinct taxa. White rot fungi and general saprotrophs
36 were most common on cellulose and xylan, while pectin and lignin-associated communities were
37 dominated by moulds, and animal pathogens were found almost exclusively on chitin. Although several
38 enzymes were produced on all biopolymers, the composition of enzyme pools was significantly different
39 among substrates and different from litter. Activity of endocellulase, β -galactosidase, β -mannosidase and
40 β -glucosidase significantly correlated with the fungal to bacterial biomass ratio indicating the important
41 role of fungi in their production. The results indicate the high level of specialization among litter-inhabiting
42 fungi and differences in the substrate preference across nutritional guilds of saprotrophic fungi. While
43 most of the litter-inhabiting fungi utilize plant biopolymers, fungal biopolymers are also frequently
44 targeted.

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46 Keywords: temperate forest; topsoil; mould; yeast; saprotroph; white rot; cellulose; chitin;
47 hemicellulose; lignin

48

50 Introduction

51 Forest soils hold one of the largest organic carbon (C) pools on Earth. While the easily available C enters
52 the soil through roots and root symbiotic fungi, recalcitrant C comes into soil in the form of plant litter,
53 dead microbial biomass or animal bodies (Baldrian 2017; Berg and McClaugherty 2003). The
54 decomposition of plant litter and dead fungal and animal material is a complex process that is key to the
55 recycling and storage of C in soil as well as the cycling of other important nutrients (Berg et al. 2001).
56 Decomposition of plant litter occurs mostly in the topsoil litter layer which also contains most fungal and
57 bacterial biomass (Baldrian 2014; Vorisková and Baldrian 2013). Thus, the understanding of organic
58 matter decomposition in the litter layer is essential for identifying factors that intervene the C global flux.
59 Plant litter is mostly composed of various complex polysaccharides such as the cellulose and
60 hemicelluloses, the phenolic lignin and pectin. Dead fungal matter includes various glucans and chitin
61 among other components (Brabcová et al. 2016). The decomposition of this dead organic matter supports
62 one of the most diverse microbial communities on Earth. Fungi, and specifically saprotrophic fungi, play a
63 critical role in the decomposition of plant litter (Boer et al. 2005; Kjøller et al. 1982; López-Mondéjar et al.
64 2018), although bacterial decomposers are also involved (Lladó et al. 2017; Lopez-Mondejar et al. 2019).
65 Although bacteria seem to be important players in the decomposition of fungal mycelia, fungi are involved
66 in this process as well (Brabcová et al. 2018; López-Mondéjar et al. 2018). Many other fungi have various
67 roles in the soil, for example, mycorrhizal fungi are obligate plant symbionts allowing the enrichment of C
68 to the soil from plant roots (Clemmensen et al. 2013). Their involvement in decomposition and the ability
69 to utilize nutrients from organic sources, such as, e.g., chitin, is, however, still a matter of debate (Lindahl
70 and Tunlid 2015). Studies of the organic matter decay process divide fungi into labile-matter specialists
71 and recalcitrant-compound decomposers (Bhatnagar et al. 2018; Lindahl et al. 2010; Moorhead and
72 Sinsabaugh 2006; Wieder et al. 2015). However, knowledge of litter-inhabiting fungi that decompose
73 specific plant and fungal biomass components, such as cellulose, xylan, glucomannan, chitin and pectin,

74 is so far limited to screening studies of enzyme production that is based on isolated strains (Baldrian et al.
75 2011; Eichlerová et al. 2015; Mašínová et al. 2018). Obviously, this approach requiring strain isolation is
76 unable to capture the nutritional preferences of all members of the soil fungal community. The utilization
77 of Stable Isotope Probing represents a potential alternative (Koechli et al. 2019; López-Mondéjar et al.
78 2018; Wilhelm et al. 2017) but it is greatly limited by the availability of ^{13}C -labelled substrates and their
79 chemical purity. As demonstrated for bacteria, enrichment of strains on certain substrate may be the right
80 way to understand nutritional preferences of soil microorganisms (López-Mondéjar et al. 2016).

81 Previous studies brought some controversy into the question whether microorganisms tend to be
82 nutritional specialists or generalists. While stable isotope probing indicates that fungi and bacteria may
83 be generalists, able to utilize various compounds (López-Mondéjar et al. 2018), the distinctive succession
84 patterns of fungal communities on decomposing litter of various age, whose chemical composition
85 changes in time (Štursová et al. 2020; Vorisková and Baldrian 2013) would indicate substrate
86 specialization. The plausible explanation would be that fungi are generalists considering the use of
87 complex substrates with various biopolymers, but specialists with respect to each biopolymer. To test this
88 hypothesis, we have here utilized high-throughput sequencing to investigate the composition of fungal
89 communities associating with various biopolymers of plant, fungal and animal origin in order to determine
90 their nutritional preferences and to classify them into substrate-related guilds as a tractable trait of certain
91 taxon that can later be associated with its presence in the environment. In this sense, “guilds” refers to
92 those fungal taxa, either phylogenetically related or non-related, which exploit the same resource
93 (Nguyen et al. 2016).

94 Enzyme activity assays and quantitative PCR were used to determine enzyme production
95 associated with various substrates and the abundance of fungi that colonize those (Nannipieri et al. 2018,
96 2019). It should be noted that – as for the Stable Isotope Probing – the association of certain fungal taxon
97 with a specific substrate should provide a sufficient proof of the incorporation of C originating from the

98 same substrate, but it does not provide an ultimate proof of the ability of its decomposition, since the
99 utilization of products of substrate decomposition by of other microbial taxa or feeding on primary
100 decomposers represent alternative ways to support fungal existence on the substrate. Still, the
101 enrichment at least demonstrates the ability of these taxa to proliferate when the particular substrate is
102 present and is indicative of the potential involvement in decomposition (Bhatnagar et al. 2018).

103

104 **Materials and methods**

105

106 **Site description, experimental set up, and sample collection**

107 The study was located in a lowland forest dominated by sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) in the Xaverovský
108 Háj Natural Reserve, North-East of Prague, Czech Republic. In addition to *Q. petraea*, *Carpinus betulus*,
109 *Tilia* spp., *Acer* spp. and *Picea abies* are also present and contribute to litter production. The soil of the
110 area is an acidic cambisol with developed litter, organic and mineral horizons. Litter exhibits pH of 4.3 with
111 46.2 % C and 1.76 % N (Šnajdr et al. 2008). The site has previously been studied with respect to litter
112 decomposition-and enzyme activity (Baldrian et al. 2010, 2013; Šnajdr et al. 2008), composition of fungal
113 communities in litter and soil (Vorisková and Baldrian 2013; Vorisková et al. 2014) and decomposition of
114 plant, fungal and bacterial biomass (López-Mondéjar et al. 2018, 2020). Four sites were selected to
115 capture the environmental variability within the forest: Site 1 (N 50° 5' 39", E 14° 37' 8"), Site 2 (N 50° 5'
116 40", E 14° 36' 58"), Site 3 (N 50° 5' 38", E 14° 36' 42"), and Site 4 (N 50° 5' 41", E 14° 36' 4"). Meshbags
117 (5x5 cm, nylon with 0.05 mm mesh) each containing 4 g of substrate were filled with one of the following
118 pure and powdered substrates: cellulose (microcrystalline ca. 0.05 mm, SERVA, Germany), xylan (from
119 beech-wood, SERVA, Germany), glucomannan (from Konjac, Natural Nutrition, USA), β -1,3-glucan (from
120 yeast cell wall concentrate, SOLGAR, USA), β -1,3-1,6-glucan (from the oyster mushroom *Pleurotus*
121 *ostreatus*, NATURES, Slovakia), lignin (lignin, alkali, Sigma-Aldrich, USA), pectin (from citrus, Alfa Aesar,

122 Germany), and chitin (from shrimp shells, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and sterilized with gamma irradiation.
123 While cellulose, xylan, glucomannan, lignin and pectin represent compounds of exclusively plant origin,
124 chitin and β -glucans are compounds found in fungal biomass, chitin being also contained in the
125 exoskeletons of arthropods (López-Mondéjar et al. 2020). Four replicate meshbags per substrate and site
126 were incubated in the bottom of the litter layer for three weeks in August/September 2018 to capture
127 microorganisms that proliferate on each substrate. The incubation of meshbags in forest soils have been
128 previously and successfully used for studying the decomposition of different C sources by the microbial
129 community inhabiting these ecosystems (Brabcová et al. 2016, 2018; Šnajdr et al. 2011; Vorisková and
130 Baldrian 2013). Meshbags were moistened with sterile water once placed in the litter horizon to promote
131 contact with surrounding litter. Upon collection after incubation, content from each meshbag was
132 retrieved and homogenized, immediately frozen with liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until DNA
133 extraction and enzymatic activities assays. Litter samples were collected from each site, cut and frozen
134 with liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C .

135

136 **Enzyme extraction and assays**

137 The activities of enzymes were assayed as previously described (Baldrian et al. 2010; Štursová and Baldrian
138 2011; Vetrovsky et al. 2011). Briefly, the activities of β -glucosidase (EC 3.2.1.21), α -glucosidase (EC
139 3.2.1.20), cellobiohydrolase (exocellulase, EC 3.2.1.91), β -xylosidase (EC 3.2.1.37), N-
140 acetylglucosaminidase (EC 3.2.1.52), β -mannosidase (exo- β -mannanase, EC 3.2.1.25), α -L-
141 arabinofuranosidase (arabinosidase, EC 3.2.1.55), and α -galactosidase (EC 3.2.1.22) were measured using
142 methylumbelliferyl substrates in sample homogenates. The activities of all other enzymes were measured
143 after their extraction with 50 ml of 50 mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.0) and desalting. Endo-1,4- β -
144 glucanase (endocellulase, EC 3.2.1.4) and endo-1,4- β -xylanase (EC 3.2.1.8) activity was measured with
145 azo-dyed carbohydrate substrates (carboxymethylcellulose and birchwood xylan, respectively) using the

146 protocol of the supplier (Megazyme, Ireland). Laccase (EC 1.10.3.2) activity was measured by monitoring
147 the oxidation of ABTS (2,2'-azinobis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid). Mn-peroxidase (EC
148 1.11.1.13) was measured using MBTH (3-methyl-2-benzothiazolinone hydrazone) and DMAB (3,3-
149 dimethylaminobenzoic acid) as substrates in the presence/absence of manganese. One unit of enzyme
150 activity was defined as the amount of enzyme catalysing the formation of 1 μmol of reaction product per
151 min.

152

153 **DNA extraction, quantitative PCR and Illumina sequencing of ITS**

154 Meshbag material subsamples were freeze-dried and 0.15 g was weighted from each subsample for total
155 DNA extraction using the FastDNA Spin Kit for soil (MP Biochemicals, USA) following the manufacturer
156 recommendations. Extractions were carried out in duplicate, and both DNA extracts from same subsample
157 were pooled.

158 Fungal 18S rRNA gene copy numbers were quantified by qPCR using the FR1/FF390 primers for
159 fungi (Chemidlin Prévost-Bouré et al. 2011). For calculating the fungal to bacteria copy ratio (F/B ratio),
160 the bacterial 16S rRNA gene copy numbers were also quantified using the 1108f and 1132r primers as
161 previously described (Vetrovsky et al. 2011).

162 Amplicon sequencing was performed as previously described (Žifčáková et al. 2016). Briefly,
163 internal transcribed spacer (ITS2) fungal DNA region was amplified using the primer pair gITS7 and ITS4
164 (Ihrmark et al. 2012). Primers contained independent barcodes on both the reverse and forward primer.
165 PCR amplification was performed in three replicates per sample. PCR reactions contained 5 μl of Q5
166 Reaction Buffer (New England Biolabs, USA), 0.75 μl of BSA (20 mg ml^{-1}), 1 μl of each primer (0.01 mM),
167 0.5 μl of PCR Nucleotide Mix (10 mM each), 0.75 μl polymerase (2 U μl^{-1} Q5 High Fidelity DNA polymerase,
168 New England Biolabs, USA), 5 μl of Q5 High GC Enhancer (New England Biolabs, USA), and 1 μl of template
169 DNA or cDNA. Cycling conditions were 94 °C for 5 min, 35 cycles of 94 °C for 1 min, 62 °C for 1 min, and

170 72 °C for 1 min, and a final extension at 72 °C for 10 min. PCR products were pooled and purified using
171 the MinElute PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, Germany), amplicon concentration was measured using a Qubit
172 2.0 Fluorometer, amplicons were pooled and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq.

173

174 **Sequence data processing and assignment of fungi to substrate-specific guilds**

175 Amplicon sequences were processed with the SEED v2.1.05 pipeline (Vetrovsky et al. 2018) as previously
176 described (Žifčáková et al. 2016). Sequence quality control involved the removal of sequencing adapters,
177 and quality and length filtering (Vestergaard et al. 2017; Schöler et al. 2017). Briefly, sequence processing
178 included merging of pair-end reads, filtering of low-quality sequences (Phred score below 30), extraction
179 of ITS2, removal of chimeras, and clustering into operational taxonomic units (OTUs) using UPARSE at a
180 similarity level of 97%. Consensus sequences were constructed for each OTU, and the closest hits at a
181 genus or species level were identified using UNITE (Nilsson et al. 2019b). Sequences identified as
182 nonfungal were discarded. Fungal sequences were assigned to the functional groups previously
183 distinguished in literature (Bödeker et al. 2016; Clemmensen et al. 2015; Sterkenburg et al. 2015): yeasts,
184 moulds, plant pathogens, animal parasites, white-rot fungi, general or litter saprotrophs (excluding yeasts
185 and moulds) and ectomycorrhizal fungi. Moulds were defined as R-strategist fungi that are not yeasts and
186 belong to the orders Eurotiales, Hypocreales, Mortierellales, Mucorales, Tremellales and Sporidiales
187 (Sterkenburg et al. 2015). The abundance data reported in this paper are based on this dataset of relative
188 abundances of ITS2 sequences and should be taken as proxies of taxon abundances only with caution
189 (Nilsson et al. 2019a). The raw reads were deposited in NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) database under
190 BioProject PRJNA643664 as submission SUB7684698.

191 Fungal OTUs were assigned to nutritional guilds based on their relative abundances in meshbags
192 with different substrates. An OTU was classified to a substrate-specific guild if its maximal relative

193 abundance in a meshbag with the respective substrate was higher than 2%, or, if its relative abundance
194 in at least five meshbags was higher than its maximal relative abundance in litter controls.

195

196 **Statistical analysis**

197 R software (RCoreTeam 2019) was used for statistical analysis. The differences in community composition
198 among treatments and sites were tested using PERMANOVA with Bonferroni correction used for pairwise
199 comparisons. Two-dimensional nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) based on Bray-Curtis
200 similarities was used to visualize the treatment effects using the package *phyloseq* (McMurdie and Holmes
201 2013). Heatmap was created using the function `heatmap.2` in the package *gplots* (Warnes et al. 2019).
202 The significance of differences in the 18S rDNA gene copies and in the fungal/bacterial ratio was
203 determined using Two-way ANOVA and the Tukey honestly significant difference post hoc test. Significant
204 differences in enzymatic activities were also tested using ANOVA and Tukey test. Pearson's correlations
205 were used as a measure of the strength of relationship between 18S gene copy abundances or fungal /
206 bacterial biomass ratios and the activities of enzymes. The values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically
207 significant.

208

209 **Results**

210

211 **Fungal colonization of the mesh bags**

212 After 3 weeks of incubation, the different substrates contained in the mesh bags were colonized by soil
213 microorganisms, although the colonization was distinct among the samples. In this sense, qPCR analyses
214 of the 18S rDNA gene abundances showed high variation in the content of fungal DNA within the samples
215 and significant differences among the substrates ($P < 0.0001$) (Fig. 1A). Cellulose and pectin contained the
216 highest amount of fungal DNA, similar to the litter where meshbags with substrates were located. β -1,3-

217 1,6-glucan and xylan showed the lowest abundance of fungi, around thousand-fold times lower than in
218 litter. The fungal to bacterial rDNA copy ratio (F/B ratio) was also significantly different among substrates
219 ($P < 0.0001$). Compared to litter, pectin-containing bags were significantly enriched in fungi while chitin-
220 containing bags contained significantly higher share of bacteria (Fig. 1B).

221 The measurements of enzymatic activities in the different substrates showed that the community
222 of microorganism associated with that substrates was able to utilize them (Fig. 2 and Supplementary Table
223 1) and the effect of substrate on the composition of enzyme pools was highly significant ($P < 0.0001$).
224 Composition of enzyme pools on all substrates was significantly different from the enzyme pool in litter.
225 In this way, bags containing cellulose (Fig. 2a), glucomannan (Fig. 2c) and glucans (Fig. 2e and 2f) showed
226 the highest activity of enzymes involved in its degradation (such as β -glucosidase and cellobiohydrolase).
227 Bags containing fungal biomass constituents (chitin, β -1,3-glucan, and β -1,3-1,6-glucan) showed high
228 activities of N-acetylglucosaminidase (2.7, 3.4 and 11.6 times higher than litter, respectively) (Fig. 2g), and
229 pectin bags presented the highest values for β -galactosidase activity (Fig. 2h). In general, the majority of
230 activities were expressed in all the substrates, with the exception of laccase activity (not detected in lignin
231 and pectin). Interestingly, in most cases, enzymatic activities in substrate bags were higher than in litter
232 (Fig. 2i). The fact that the activity of cellobiohydrolase, β -galactosidase, β -mannosidase and β -glucosidase
233 significantly correlated with the fungal to bacterial biomass ratio and the absence of correlation between
234 bacterial abundance and enzyme activity indicates the importance of fungi for enzyme production
235 (Supplementary Figure S1).

236

237 **Fungal communities associated with biopolymers**

238 The composition of the fungal community was significantly influenced by the type of substrate ($P <$
239 0.0001), the site ($P < 0.0001$) and their interaction ($P < 0.0001$). However, the substrate explained 35.4%
240 of the total variability, while site and interaction explained only 9.3% and 9.1%, respectively. Communities

241 of fungi in meshbags of all substrates were significantly different from each other as well as from the
242 control litter ($P < 0.001$). The higher influence of substrate over the effect of sites was also apparent from
243 the NMDS (Fig. 3). The composition of the fungal communities in pectin, lignin and chitin was similar along
244 all the samples for each substrate, as it was in the case of the fungal community inhabiting litter. In the
245 rest of substrates, fungal communities were more variable showing higher contribution of the site effect.

246 Despite the differences among samples, our results showed that the fungal communities
247 colonizing each substrate were similar across the four sites both regarding the classification to functional
248 guilds (Fig. 4A) and taxonomic composition (Fig. 4B). In this sense, sequences of moulds dominated the
249 communities in all substrates except cellulose, xylan and glucomannan. Their relative share was especially
250 high on pectin (90%), lignin (48%) and chitin (47%). The major genera enriched across multiple substrates
251 included *Penicillium*, *Trichoderma*, *Mortierella*, *Backusella*, *Mucor* and *Talaromyces* (Fig. 4B). White rot
252 fungi (represented mostly by the genus *Sistotrema*) were especially high (>20%) on cellulose, xylan and β -
253 1,3-glucan, while they were virtually absent from pectin, lignin and chitin. Glucomannan was relatively
254 enriched with plant pathogens (35%, mainly genera *Cosmospora* and *Alternaria*) and chitin with animal
255 parasites (20%, *Pochonia*, *Lecanicillium*). Yeasts, represented mostly by the genera *Apiotrichum* and
256 *Pishurozyma*, were most common on glucomannan where the relative abundance of their sequences was
257 11% (Fig. 4). Finally, ectomycorrhizal fungi that represented 2.5% of sequences were virtually absent from
258 all substrates (mean abundance between 0.0% and 0.2%) (Fig. 4).

259

260 **Nutritional guilds of fungi in forest litter**

261 In total 272 fungal OTUs were found enriched on at least one substrate and were thus classified to one or
262 multiple nutritional guilds. Of them, 48 taxa were assigned to cellulose, 79 to glucomannan, 71 to lignin,
263 59 to β -1,3-1,6-glucan, 72 to pectin, 77 to chitin, 88 to xylan and 92 to β -1,3-glucan (Supplementary Table
264 S2).

265 In total, these taxa accounted for the 40% of the abundance in litter; although the relative
266 abundance of sequences of each nutritional guild was different (Fig. 5). Sequences of fungi classified to
267 the nutritional guilds of xylan, lignin, β -1,3-glucan and chitin showed high relative abundance in litter,
268 accounting for 26.4%, 26.2%, 25.7%, and 25.6%, respectively. On the contrary, sequences of fungi
269 classified to the nutritional guilds of β -1,3-1,6-glucan, pectin and cellulose were rarer in the litter (6.2%,
270 6.6%, and 7.2%). Across sites, considerable level of variation in the share of nutritional guilds was
271 observed: for example, the values for the glucomannan guild ranged from 6 to 40% across litter samples.
272 Around half of the total selected taxa (52.2%) were found only in one of the substrates (Supplementary
273 Table S2). The rest of taxa appeared in two or more substrates, but another 30.5% were still constrained
274 only to 2 or 3 substrates. The percentage for taxa growing in more than 4 substrates was low (17.3%), and
275 none of the OTUs was classified to all nutritional guilds. By substrates, cellulose, pectin and chitin showed
276 the highest percentage of unique OTUs (33.3%, 33.3%, and 32.5%, respectively), followed by glucomannan
277 (25.3%), lignin (22.5%) and xylan (20.4%). Both glucans, β -1,3- and β -1,3-1,6-, showed the lowest
278 proportion of unique OTUs, 16.3% and 13.6% respectively. The specificity of the fungal community was
279 also observed when comparing the taxa overlapping between the different substrates. In the case of
280 compounds of fungal origin (chitin, β -1,3-glucan and β -1,3-1,6-glucan), only the 6.2% of the taxa were
281 shared (Fig. 6A). Similar results were found when comparing the guilds associated with the different
282 components of plant biomass. In this way, the most abundant components, cellulose and hemicelluloses,
283 only shared the 7.3% of the OTUs (Fig. 6B). The overlap was even lower when comparing cellulose with
284 other important components from plant biomass such as lignin and pectin, where less than 1% of the taxa
285 were shared (Fig. 6B). Similar patterns are showed when comparing the 20 most abundant OTUs in each
286 substrate (Fig. 6C). Several groups of taxa seem to appear only on one substrate, being easily identified
287 for pectin (dominated mainly by strains of *Penicillium* and *Talaromyces*), lignin (strains of *Penicillium* and
288 *Nectria*), chitin (*Lecanicillium* and *Mortierella*), cellulose (strains of *Ceratobasidium* and *Dactyella*) and β -

289 1,3-1,6-glucan (dominated by strains of *Trichoderma*). The fungal communities degrading xylan, β -1,3-
290 glucan and glucomannan shared higher numbers of OTUs. On the other hand, some taxa were identified
291 as generalists that were highly enriched across multiple substrates, such as some members of the genera
292 *Trichoderma*, *Apiotrichum*, *Backusella*, *Alternaria* and *Chaetomium*.

293

294 **Discussion**

295 Our results showed that fungal decomposer communities are composed of both specialist and generalist
296 taxa. A previous study using bulky substrates of plant, bacterial and fungal origin indicated that the
297 percentage of generalists was rather high, similar to the number of specialists in the decomposer
298 communities in forest soils (López-Mondéjar et al. 2018). The same study showed, however, that
299 generalists represented the most abundant members of the community, therefore indicating that the
300 guilds of decomposers specialized for different substrates were not common in the forest soils. In
301 accordance with our initial hypothesis we show that the level of specialization of fungi with respect to the
302 association of individual biopolymers is much higher.

303 The abundant generalist taxa of fungi inhabiting forest soils belong mostly to moulds and yeasts
304 (López-Mondéjar et al. 2018). In our study, moulds accounted for a quarter of the total fungal abundance
305 in the litter samples, most likely due to the high amount of organic matter present in the forest floor of
306 our study site. Their ability to grow fast allows them to rapidly colonize and use simple substrates, what
307 explain their high abundance on substrates such as pectin (almost 90%), β -glucans (33-40%) and
308 glucomannan (23%). Importantly, not all the taxa classified as moulds were found to be generalists with
309 respect to individual biopolymers. Many of them, such as the OTUs assigned to *Penicillium*, were only
310 abundant in one of the substrates. Similar results were previously found in species of *Penicillium*, which
311 are metabolically variable due mostly to niche differentiation (Baldrian et al. 2011). Interestingly, moulds
312 were also abundant in more complex substrates, especially in lignin (around 41%), despite previous

313 studies showed that they present low activity for enzymes like laccase, related to the degradation of
314 recalcitrant phenolic polymers of lignin (Eichlerová et al. 2015). The presence of other ecophysiological
315 groups of fungi encoding a more complex enzymatic system, such as saprotrophs (36%) and yeasts (2.3%),
316 could mediate the liberation of simpler compounds presented in Kraft lignin which are rapidly assimilated
317 by moulds. This hypothesis is supported by the detection of high enzymatic activities involved in the use
318 of simple substrates in lignin bags (Fig. 2d). The profile of enzymatic production in lignin bags (showing
319 the lowest Mn-peroxidase activity and no laccase activity) may also explain why white-rot fungi, a fungal
320 group specialized in the decomposition of this polymer had low abundance in lignin bags. Unlike the rest
321 of polymers tested in this study, which are homo- and heteropolysaccharides composed of sugar units
322 bound by glycosidic linkages, lignin is a highly complex heteropolymer consisting of different units linked
323 together by a variety of carbon-carbon (C-C) and aryl-ether (C-O-C) linkages. Due to this random
324 phenylpropanoic polymeric structure, the mineralization process of lignin may take many years (Janusz et
325 al. 2013). In addition to its high recalcitrance, it is important to highlight that in our experiment lignin was
326 the only source of C in the respective meshbags. In nature, lignin is normally covalently linked to other
327 cell wall components such as hemicelluloses and the rapid breakdown of these other more easily
328 decomposable C sources accelerate the degradation of lignin (Klotzbucher et al. 2011). Therefore, since
329 the incubation of this recalcitrant lignin took only three weeks, these bags were likely at the very initial
330 phase of degradation, being colonized by other fungal groups such as saprotrophs with a faster growth
331 than the white-rot fungi, whose abundance is expected to increase in later phases of lignin degradation.
332 Therefore, it is worth to point out that the presence of a taxon in a certain substrate may not indicate
333 directly an evidence of its role in decomposition. The occurrence of other phenomena like the processes
334 of cross-feeding, cheating and generation of secondary colonies during the incubation time, beside the
335 participation of other players in the decomposition, such as bacteria, have to be taken into account.

336 Despite the abundance of generalist moulds in all the substrates, we show that there is a high
337 degree of specialization among fungal saprotrophs and each substrate is preferred by a distinct, specific
338 community. Similar results were recently shown when studying the decay of various litter types
339 (Bhatnagar et al. 2018). These authors found that species were organized into functional guilds of
340 decomposers for cellulose and lignin, which were composed by at least 100 taxa including both dominant
341 and rare ones. In our study, different guilds were also observed for the different components of plant
342 biomass such as cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin and pectin, although the number of taxa in these guilds
343 was lower due to only the abundant taxa were kept for the analysis. The decomposer guild for cellulose
344 was dominated by saprotrophs and white-rot fungi, meanwhile plant pathogens were also involved in the
345 degradation of hemicelluloses. Some of these saprotrophic taxa such as *Aureobasidium* and *Cladosporium*
346 are well known as inhabitant of the leaves phyllosphere that persist till early decomposition stages
347 (Bonanomi et al. 2019; Voriskova and Baldrian 2013), supporting the hypothesis that certain taxa may
348 change from endophytism to a saprotrophic strategy. White-rot fungi have been previously reported as
349 highly potent producers of cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic enzymes, containing numerous genes
350 encoding glycosyl hydrolases involved in the degradation of cellulose and hemicellulose (Alfaro et al. 2014;
351 Eichlerová et al. 2015; Sista Kameshwar and Qin 2018; Bentil 2018). In the same way, the abundance of
352 plant pathogens in hemicelluloses but not in cellulose could be related with a lower number of genes
353 encoding cellulolytic enzymes in their genomes (Alfaro et al. 2014; Zhao et al. 2013). Plant pathogens lack
354 of important plant cell wall degrading enzymes for efficiently degrading cellulose, but still present the
355 ability to degrade less recalcitrant components in plant biomass such hemicelluloses (King et al. 2011;
356 Kubicek et al. 2014; Zhao et al. 2013). Interestingly, plant pathogens were also abundant in β -1,3- and β -
357 1,3-1,6-glucans, despite these components had fungal origin and are mostly found in fungi. β -glucans are
358 an important type of hemicelluloses, mainly having β -1,4- links such in xyloglucans but also β -1,3-1,4- links
359 in mixed glucans (Zhou et al. 2017). The structural similarity among the fungal β -glucans and the

360 hemicellulosic β -glucans would explain the ability of fungi for degrading all these compounds. Indeed,
361 xylan, glucomannan and β -glucans showed the highest similarities in their communities (Fig. 6C). Since
362 the composition of hemicellulosic matrix in plant biomass is highly variable and contains numerous
363 polysaccharides presenting different links, the ability of degrading more than just one type of their
364 components may be a common and useful trait. On the contrary, cellulose (specially the crystalline
365 cellulose used in our study) is a very recalcitrant substrate, as was previously showed (López-Mondéjar et
366 al. 2018). Its decomposition is mainly carried out by a specific community of real decomposers dominated
367 by the saprotrophs (almost the 50% of the community). This ability is relatively common among the
368 saprotrophic Ascomycota and Basidiomycota and many saprotrophic species have been reported to
369 contain cellobiohydrolase, the enzyme essential in the deconstruction of cellulose (Baldrian et al. 2012;
370 Stursova et al. 2012).

371 Finally, chitin, one of the main components of fungal biomass, also supported a specific guild of
372 decomposers. In this way, animal parasites, that were slightly 2% in the total community in litter,
373 increased up to the 20% only in this substrate. Although the decomposition of chitin is a common trait in
374 most fungi because the chitinase activity is involved in the morphogenesis of their own mycelia, the
375 production of endochitinases that efficiently cleave chitin is much less common (Baldrian et al. 2011).
376 Moulds and saprotrophs have previously been reported to be involved in the degradation of fungal
377 biomass in forest soils, but the activity of some abundant taxa was related with the degradation of other
378 components of fungal biomass rather than chitin (Brabcova et al. 2016; Brabcová et al. 2018). Two
379 abundant genera in this guild, *Pochonia* and *Lecanicillium*, are well known as high producers of chitinases
380 (Halder et al. 2019). Interestingly, some of the specific taxa in the chitin guild such as *Mortierella* and
381 *Pochonia* have been recently showed to be linked to mites in forest soils and being involved in the
382 degrading of dead biomass of arthropods in these ecosystems (Werner et al. 2018).

383 Despite yeasts have been shown to be involved in the degradation of plant and fungal biomass in
384 forest floor, their abundance in all the tested substrates was low, ranging from values between 1 and 3%.
385 It is commonly assumed that their unicellular nature results in a lower efficiency for using bulky,
386 recalcitrant substrates than filamentous fungi. Still, taxa from the genera *Apiotrichum* have been
387 abundantly found in litter from oak forests being involved in the degradation of phenolic compounds
388 (Masinova et al. 2017). This ability to degrade complex and resistant substances could explain their
389 presence in lignin, and in general, the higher abundance of yeasts in soil than in litter, where more
390 recalcitrant organic matter is accumulated (Masinova et al. 2017).

391 Looking at the litter-inhabiting community of fungi, it should be noted that twelve of the twenty
392 most abundant litter fungi did not belong to any decomposer guild. Similar results were reported recently
393 by Bhatnagar et al. (2018). Since most of these fungi in our litter were saprotrophs, these results may
394 indicate that several fungi have more complex requirements for the colonization of a specific substrate.
395 It can be the lack of mineral nutrients like N and P in the pure substrates, the preference of a complex
396 biomass or the utilization of other compounds than those tested, e.g., proteins, fatty acids or simple
397 organic molecules. It was also interesting to observe that the share of nutritional guild members in litter
398 is highly inhomogeneous, for example the fungi associating with β -1,3-glucan represented between 8 and
399 41% of the litter community across the studied area (Figure 3). These results support the view of the forest
400 litter as a highly spatially heterogeneous environment with highly uneven activity of decomposition-
401 related enzymes (Baldrian 2014; Šnajdr et al. 2008) and probably also varying distribution of the members
402 of the decomposer community (Navrátilová et al. 2017; Štursova et al. 2016).

403

404 **Conclusions**

405 Linking community composition and functionality is still a challenging step for understanding the
406 biogeochemical processes involved in the transformation of organic matter in forest soils. Saprotroph

407 fungi are the main decomposer in these ecosystems, being directly responsible for the recycle of nutrients,
408 C and the rest of elements. Despite the fact that our study was based on just three weeks incubations and
409 temporal dynamics in fungal/microbial communities occur in forest soils, we clearly showed that
410 saprotrophic fungi from various nutritional guilds differed in their affinity to various components of
411 organic matter. The classification of decomposer fungi into different guilds sheds light into how the
412 different microbial species are controlling the decomposition processes and their involvement in the C
413 turnover in forest soils. We highly recommend utilizing similar approaches across a wide variety of
414 environments to build a database of functional traits that will aid the understanding of fungal community
415 functioning based on its taxonomic composition. This information will be extremely valuable for improving
416 the models of the C cycling in terrestrial ecosystems and for enhancing the future predictions about the
417 exchanges of C between biosphere and atmosphere in the current context of climate change.

418

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426

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587 in ecosystem properties between summer and winter. *Environ Microbiol* 18:288–301

588

589 **Figures**

590

591 Figure 1. A) Relative abundance of fungi expressed as the 18S rDNA gene counts and (B) the
592 fungal/bacterial biomass ratio in the different mesh bags. The boxplots show medians, upper and lower

593 quartiles, upper and lower bounds and values for individual samples across all four sites (n=16). Statistically
594 significant differences across substrates are indicated by different letters.

595

596 Figure 2. Activity of enzymes in mesh bags with biopolymers after incubation in the forest topsoil for three
597 weeks and in the surrounding litter. The data represent the averages and standard errors (n=16). Activity
598 expressed as mU per gram of dry mass.

599

600 Figure 3. Composition of fungal communities established in bags with various substrates incubated in the
601 *Quercus petraea* topsoil and in litter. 2D-Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) on Bray Curtis
602 similarities.

603

604 Figure 4. Fungal community composition in bags with substrates and in the litter of the *Quercus petraea*
605 forest. Averages of the four bags from each site are shown. A) Abundance of the nutritional guilds in each
606 substrate and in litter. B) Abundance of the main genera in each substrate and in litter. The number
607 indicates the site.

608

609 Figure 5. Relative abundance of fungi belonging to different nutritional guilds in the litter of the *Quercus*
610 *petraea* forest. The boxplots show medians, upper and lower quartiles, upper and lower bounds and values
611 for individual samples across all four sites (n=16).

612

613 Figure 6. The share of fungal OTUs in the *Quercus petraea* forest utilizing multiple substrates within the
614 components of fungal origin (A) and within the main components of plant biomass (B). The numbers
615 represent the percentage of the OTUs that appeared in one or more substrates. The absence of number

616 indicates that no OTUs were shared between those substrates. C) Relative abundance of the fungal OTUs
617 on different substrates. Only the twenty most abundant OTUs from each substrate are shown.

618

619 **Supplementary Files.**

620 Supplementary Table S1. Activity of enzymes in the mesh bags containing different substrates. Activities
621 expressed in mU per gram of dry mass (n=16). The data represent means and standard errors (n=16).
622 Activities in bold were significantly different among the substrates. Statistically significant differences
623 among enzyme activities across substrates are indicated by different letters.

624 Supplementary Table S2. List of the OTUs assigned to nutritional guilds. Only OTUs showing maximal
625 relative abundance in a meshbag with the respective substrate higher than 2%, or, presenting higher
626 relative abundance in at least five meshbags than its maximal relative abundance in litter controls are
627 included.

628 Supplementary Figure S1. Person's correlations measuring the strength of relationship between 18S copy
629 abundance or F/B ratio and the enzymatic activities. Only values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically
630 significant and colored. The activity of cellobiohydrolase, β -galactosidase, β -mannosidase and β -
631 glucosidase were significantly correlated with the F/B ratio. No correlation was found between bacterial
632 abundance and enzymatic activities.

633